

Supplementary material – data extraction form

This data extraction form is developed from Cochrane’s “Data collection form for intervention reviews: RCTs and non-RCTs” (1)

General Information

Date form completed (<i>dd/mm/yyyy</i>)	30-09-2022	
Name/ID of person extracting data	MDL	
Author(s)	Saha et al.	
Country of origin	Türkiye	
Publication year	2021	
Title of article	The Effect of Computer-Based Training on Self-care and Daily Living Activities in Patients With Lumbar Discectomy Surgery	
Title of journal	Comput Inform Nurs.	
Volume Sep 133	Issue 40(3)	Pages 147-153
Publication type (<i>e.g. full report, abstract, letter</i>)	Scientific article	

Study eligibility

Study Characteristics	Eligibility criteria <i>There are no restrictions on the types of study.</i>				Location in text or source (<i>pg & ¶/fig/table/other</i>)
		Yes	No	Unclear	
Type of study	Randomised Controlled Trial	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Subtitle, abstract, p. 148
	Quasi-randomised Controlled Trial	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Controlled Before and After Study	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Other design (specify):	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Participants	Lumbar disc surgery patients	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 148
Types of intervention	Computer-Based Training on Self-care and Daily Living Activities	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Title, abstract, p. 149-150
Types of comparison	Control group, routine discharge training	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 150
Types of outcome measures	Function disability/status Self-care ability	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 148-149

INCLUDE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EXCLUDE <input type="checkbox"/>
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Characteristics of included studies

Methods

	Descriptions as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Aim of study (e.g. efficacy, equivalence, pragmatic)	The aim of this study was to determine the effect of computer-based discharge training on patients with lumbar disc surgery on self-care agency and independence in daily living activities.	p. 148
Design (e.g. parallel, crossover, non-RCT)	RCT	Subtitle, abstract, p. 148
Start date	September 2018	p. 148
End date	October 2019	p. 148
Ethical approval needed/ obtained for study	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unclear Necessary permissions were obtained from the University of Health Sciences Ethics Committee	p. 150

Participants

	Description <i>Include comparative information for each intervention or comparison group if available</i>	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Setting (including location and social context)	The neurosurgery clinic of a training and research hospital	
Inclusion criteria	(1) age of 18 years and over, (2) planned elective lumbar disc surgery, (3) literate and not having vision and hearing loss, (4) possession of and ability to use technological products for education, (5) no communication problems, and (6) agreement to participate in the study.	p. 148
Exclusion criteria	Patients with any orthopedic disease were excluded from the study.	p. 148
Informed consent obtained	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unclear Written informed consent was obtained from the patients who met the inclusion criteria, and the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki were adhered to during the research.	p. 150

Intervention group

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Intervention group	Abstract, p. 148-152
No. randomised to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	N=30 (M:15, F:15) Mean age = 48.9	Table 1, p. 151 Table 1, p. 151
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	<p>The computer-based lumbar disc surgery discharge training video was opened from the researcher's computer at least 1 hour before the patients were discharged, and the training was given face-to-face in the seminar room. Patients were trained for 30 minutes on providing a safe environment to prevent falls, deep breathing and coughing exercises, recommendations for nutrition and excretory, principles of correct body mechanics in daily life activities, the postoperative recovery process, necessary exercise, driving, and returning to work. The patient's relatives were also included in the training. During the training, the patients' and their relatives' questions were answered, and aspects were explained again when necessary.</p> <p>The training content was delivered to the patients after the training, loaded on a CD. The patients were shown how to use the training material at home in practice. Patients were called to remind them to watch the training CD once per week.</p>	p. 149-150

Control group

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Control group	Abstract,
No. randomised to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	N=30 (M:19, F:11) Mean age = 49.03	Table 1, p. 151 Table 1, p. 151
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	Routine discharge training was performed in the clinic by the nurse. In the routine training, the patients were only informed about lying, getting out of bed, lying positions in bed, and providing a safe environment. In the routine practice of the clinic, education was also given to the patients and their relatives.	Abstract, p. 150

Outcomes

Outcome 1

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Functional status	p. 148
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Modified Barthel Index (MBI) No difference	p. 148

Outcome 2

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Individuals self-care ability	p. 149
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Exercise of Self-Care Agency Scale (ESCA) Favors intervention	p. 149

Follow up

Follow up	6 weeks	p. 4
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Conclusion

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Conclusion	<p>Results: The increase in the modified Barthel Index and Exercise of Self-Care Agency Scale scores after training in the intervention and control groups were statistically significant ($P < .001$). The increase in Exercise of Self-Care Agency Scale scores after the training was found to be higher in the intervention group than in the control group. There was no difference between the modified Barthel Index mean scores before and after the training between the groups ($P > .05$). Computer-based discharge training improved the participants' independence in their daily living activities and increased the self-care power of the patients compared with the control group.</p> <p>Conclusions: According to this study, there was no difference between the independence in daily living activities of patients who received computer-based education and routine education, but it was observed that self-care agency was higher in patients who received computer-based education. Accordingly, it is important for nurses to provide discharge training by using technology and determining the appropriate training method for patients and their relatives because it facilitates learning and increases the effectiveness of education. It is recommended that the methods used in patient education should be chosen according to the independence and learning needs of individuals, computer-based video training material should be developed for individuals with lumbar disc surgery, and studies should be performed in larger sample groups with a longer follow-up period.</p>	Abstract, p. 152

References

1. Cochrane. Data collection form for intervention reviews for RCTs and non-RCTs - template [Internet]. The Cochrane Collaboration. 2022 [cited 2022 Sep 15]. Available from: <https://dplp.cochrane.org/data-extraction-forms>